

Factors Associated with Limited Level of Health Literacy on Application of Health Information Related to Opioid Use in Kachin State, Myanmar

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Abstract

Introduction: Opioid abuse has caused immense suffering for people in Myanmar especially in Kachin and Shan States. Promoting health literacy relevant to opioid use can lessen those problems but little is known about opioid literacy level of general population. Thus, objectives of this study were to find out the prevalence of literacy level on application of health information relevant to opioid use and the factors affecting the limited level of opioid literacy among adult males in Kachin State, Myanmar.

Method and Materials: A total of 327 adult males in Kachin State who had never used illicit drugs were selected for this cross-sectional study. A sub-scale of the European Health Literacy Questionnaire, HLS-EU-Q47, was adapted to assess the level of application on opioid-related health information. Data were collected from July to August 2019 through face to face interview with the participants. Multiple logistic analysis was performed to find out the association.

Result: 61.47% of the participants had limited level of literacy in terms of application of opioid-related health information. The findings indicated that not being Bamar (AOR= 3.61, 95% CI = 1.97-6.63, p <0.001), being unemployed (AOR=2.44, 95% CI= 1.38-4.30, p <0.01) and not having siblings who used opioids (AOR=2.47, 95% CI= 1.10-5.56, p <0.05) were more likely to have limited level of literacy in terms of applying opioid-related health information.

Discussion: Socioeconomic and environmental factors had influence on health literacy especially application of health information relevant to opioid use. It is important to take appropriate measures to improve opioid-related health literacy particularly among the vulnerable groups to help prevent them from drug use and its problems.

Keywords: *Opioids, Health Literacy, Males, Kachin, Myanmar.*

Introduction

Opioid abuse is a serious public health and safety concern around the world which has significant impact on health and welfare of human^[1]. Myanmar stood second in producing opium around the world and bore the heavy brunt of opioid abuse^[2]. Kachin was one of the most opium producing states in Myanmar and had socioeconomic burden of drug use. A qualitative study of Oo and Doe^[3] stated that not only drug users but also the family members suffered health, socioeconomic and marital problems such as acquiring HIV/AIDS,

discrimination from their communities and domestic violence. Moreover, drug use also caused a real predicament for the whole society^[4].

Health literacy is one of the fundamentals for health system where more active role of individuals in decisions and management is required^[5]. As it is a strong indicator for measuring people's health^[6], promoting it relevant to opioid use would be helpful to lessen the drug abuse problems. As stated by Shuja et al^[7], an increase in health literacy of people could enhance their knowledge on consequences of illicit drugs which could then resulted

in not using those substances. In fact, health literacy is way beyond being able to read health information and understand them. It empowers people by developing their capacity to apply the information effectively^[8].

Until now, little is known about opioid-related health literacy in general population. Therefore, this study aimed to find out the prevalence of literacy level on application of health information relevant to opioid use and the factors affecting the limited level of opioid literacy among adult males in Kachin State, Myanmar. By knowing these factors related to opium literacy, it would be helpful for local authorities and civil society organizations to implement effective interventions to promote health literacy in order to reduce drug use problems.

Methodology

Study Design: This cross-sectional study was conducted to identify factors associated with limited literacy on application of opioid-related health information among adult males in Kachin State, Myanmar. Only adult males were included in this study because it was part of an Independent Study, namely, “a case-control study on risk factors of opioid use”, which was carried out among adult male opioid users and non-drug users.

Study Subjects: The sample size in this study was 327 which was estimated from the method of Fleiss with a continuity correction for the above-mentioned case-control study^[9]. Participants were adult males (18 years or above) who had never used illicit drugs. They were simple randomly selected from general population in Kachin State, Myanmar through local government’s household registration. The exclusion criteria were the people with serious physical and mental problems as well as those who were not able to verbally communicate with interviewers.

Data collection: A structured questionnaire which contained socioeconomic and demographic characteristics, opioid-related information (environmental factors) and index of health literacy on applying opioid-related health information was used to collect data from the adult males. Face to face interviews were carried out by the trained interviewers with written guideline. Verbal consent was obtained from the participants before the interview.

Data analysis: Data analysis was carried out by using Stata 14.2. The categorical data were described by using frequency and percentage whereas the continuous data were reported as mean and median. For inferential statistics, bivariate analysis was conducted to identify the factors associated with limited level of literacy in terms of applying opioid-related health. The factors with $p < 0.25$ were continued into the final model or multivariate analysis^[10].

Ethical Approval: This research was approved by Khon Kean University Ethics Committee in Human research, (Approval number HE622140 4.3.03: 20/2019).

Results

Descriptive Analysis: The study contained 327 adult males who had never used illicit drugs. Most of the participants were between the age of 20 to 39 years (45.57%) with the average age of 35 years. Half of them (50.76%) were single whereas 44.34% were married. Regarding educational level, 57.49% were in secondary education and 30.58% were in university level. Majority of participants were Kachin (70.64%) and Christians (76.76%), and Bamar and Buddhists constituted 19.27% and 21.1% respectively. Most of the participants (85.32%) believed and practised their religions. More than 30% were unemployed and about 14% were unskilled workers. Over half of the respondents earned 100,000 kyats or less monthly. Only about 18% lived in rural areas and about 35% migrated from other places. Alcohol (43.12%) was the most consumed substance for respondents followed by smoking cigarettes or cheroots (30.58%) and chewing betel nuts (10.70%).

Prevalence of limited health literacy level on applying opioid-related health information: Opioid-related health literacy on applying the information was assessed by modifying 11 questions of HLS-EU-Q47 (only “apply information” sub-scale). A four-point Likert scale was used for the answers – very difficult, fairly difficult, fairly easy and very easy with the score of 1 to 4 respectively. Recommended scoring system from the formula: $\text{Index} = (\text{mean} - 1) \times 50/3$ which score ranged from 0 to 50 was utilized⁽¹¹⁾. According to the score, the participants were categorized into four groups: inadequate (0 to 25), problematic (26 to 33), sufficient (34 to 42) and excellent (43 to 50). To explore the vulnerable group, the first two levels were combined as a group and named as limited health literacy^(11,12,13). As shown in Table 1, more than 60% had limited literacy.

Table 1. Prevalence of Limited Health Literacy Level on Applying Information Relevant to Opioids among the Participants (n = 327)

Apply information relevant to Opioid-related Health Information	Frequency	Percentage
Limited (0-33)	201	61.47
Sufficient (34-42)	90	27.52
Excellent (43-50)	36	11.01

Factors associated with limited level of literacy on applying opioid-related health information among adult males: A bivariate analysis: In the simple logistic regression analysis, eight factors were found to be associated with the limited opioid literacy ($p < 0.25$). They were young and old aged people (COR= 2.27, 95% CI= 1.34 to 3.86), ethnic groups other than Bamar (COR= 4.29, 95% CI= 2.39 to 7.69), not being Buddhists (COR=

3.49, 95% CI= 2.01 to 6.06), being unemployed (COR= 2.90, 95% CI= 1.70 to 4.94), earning inadequate income (COR= 1.62, 95% CI= 1.02 to 2.58), not chewing betel quid (COR= 4.06, 95% CI= 1.91 to 8.63), being born in the study place (COR= 1.61, 95% CI= 1.01 to 2.57) and not having siblings who used drugs (COR= 1.68, 95% CI= 0.79 to 3.56). Table 2 shows the crude association between these variables and limited opioid literacy.

Table 2. Odds Ratio for each category of factors associated with limited level of literacy on application of health information on opioid use: a bivariate analysis (n= 327)

Characteristics	Number	% of people with limited health literacy	Crude OR	95%CI	p-value
1. Age					0.0018
Middle age (20-59)	233	56.22	1		
Young and old age	94	74.47	2.27	1.34 to 3.86	
2. Ethnicity					0.0000
Bamar	63	33.33	1		
Other ethnic groups	264	68.18	4.29	2.39 to 7.69	
3. Religion					0.0000
Buddhist	69	37.68	1		
Christian and others	258	67.83	3.49	2.01 to 6.06	
4. Employment Status					0.0000
Employed	225	54.22	1		
Unemployed	102	77.45	2.90	1.70 to 4.94	
5. Financial Situation					0.0391
Enough	195	56.92	1		
Not enough	132	68.18	1.62	1.02 to 2.58	
6. Betel quid					0.0001
Yes	35	31.43	1		
No	292	65.07	4.06	1.91 to 8.63	
7. Migration status					0.0441
Move from other places	113	53.98	1		
Born here	214	65.42	1.61	1.01 to 2.57	
8. Opioids use by siblings					0.1809
Yes	30	50.00	1		
No	297	62.63	1.68	0.79 to 3.56	

Factors associated with limited level of literacy on applying opioid-related health information among adult males: A multivariate analysis: Eight variables from bivariate analysis were proceeded to multivariable analysis by using multiple logistic regression with backward elimination. After the analysis, three factors:

being ethnic groups other than Bamar (AOR= 3.61, 95%CI= 1.97-6.63, $p < 0.001$), being unemployed (AOR= 2.44, 95% CI= 1.38-4.30, $p < 0.01$) and not having siblings who used opioids (AOR= 2.47, 95% CI= 1.10-5.56, $p < 0.05$) were significantly associated with the limited opioid literacy, see Table 3.

Table 3. Odds Ratio for each category of factors associated with limited level of literacy on application of health information on opioid use: a multivariable analysis (n= 327)

Characteristics	Number	% of people with limited health literacy	Crude OR (95%CI)	Adjusted OR (95%CI)	p-value
1. Ethnicity					< 0.001
Bamar	63	33.33	1		
Other ethnic groups	264	68.18	4.29(2.39 to 7.69)	3.61(1.97 to 6.63)	
2. Employment status					< 0.01
Employed	225	54.22	1		
Unemployed	102	77.45	2.90(1.70 to 4.94)	2.44(1.38 to 4.30)	
3. Opioid use by siblings					< 0.05
Yes	30	50.00	1		
No	297	62.63	1.68(0.79 to 3.56)	2.47(1.10 to 5.56)	

Discussion

The study observed that limited level of health literacy on application of opioid-related health information was more than 60% which was 10% higher than the finding in a cross-sectional study among 1367 participants from 35 townships⁽¹⁴⁾ The latter conducted in different areas but not included Kachin State. Another study reported that limited health literacy in healthcare settings of Southeast Asia countries was found to be higher, with 67.5%⁽¹⁵⁾. Thus, the reason why Kachin State had lower level of satisfactory health literacy may be due to inaccessibility of health services, but it may also be because of the low sample size of the study. The review study in Southeast Asia⁽¹⁵⁾ also reported the high discrepancies in showing prevalence of limited literacy by the studies, varied from 1.6% to 99.5%.

The study also found out that socioeconomic (ethnicity, unemployment) and environmental factors (not having siblings who used illicit drugs) had significant associations with the limited level of opium literacy on applying health information. Kachin and other ethnic groups were likelier to have limited health literacy than Bamar (AOR= 3.61, 95%CI= 1.97-6.63, $p < 0.001$). Bamar constituted the most proportion of ethnic groups in the whole country, meaning that ethnic groups

with less proportion had limited literacy. Unemployed persons were more prone to have limited literacy than employed people (AOR= 2.44, 95% CI= 1.38-4.30, $p < 0.01$). A health survey in Catalonia also reported that limited literacy was associated with low socioeconomic status which included unemployment (AOR= 2.11, CI 95%= 1.42–3.15, $p < 0.001$)⁽¹⁶⁾. Pedro, Amaral and Escoval⁽¹⁷⁾ also mentioned that unemployed people were among vulnerable groups to have limited literacy. As students were also included in unemployed status, they should also be considered in providing health education. The last factor associated with limited application on health information was not having siblings who used opioids (AOR= 2.47, 95% CI= 1.10-5.56, $p < 0.05$). They might not understand well about opioid issues as they may not see the problem around them.

Limitation of the Study: This study covers Kachin state only so the similar studies should be conducted in other states such as Shan State where opioid problems are prominent. As general limitation, this cross-sectional study measured exposures and the outcome at the same time and thus, causal relationship between them could not be identified. Moreover, as it included adult males only, other populations such as females, adolescents and the drug users were not represented in this research.

Conclusion

It was observed that limited level of opium literacy on applying health information was associated with the vulnerable members of the community – ethnic groups rather than Bamar, unemployed people and those who did not have drug user siblings. It is important to take appropriate measures to improve opioid-related health literacy particularly among the vulnerable groups to help prevent them from drug use and its problems. When providing health education, languages that different ethnic groups can understand should be used so that they can understand the drug problems and their adverse effects.

Conflicting Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this research.

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References

1. United Nations Office for Drugs and Crime. "Understanding the global opioid crisis", Global Smart Update Volume 21. [internet]. 2019 [cited 2019 Nov 16]. Available from: https://www.unodc.org/documents/scientific/Global_SMART_21_web_new.pdf
2. Al Jazeera News. Myanmar cracking down on opium, but conflicts push drug trade. [internet]. 2019 Jan 11 [cited 2019 Nov 16]. Available from: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2019/01/myanmar-cracking-opium-conflicts-fuel-drug-trade-190110083026170.html>
3. Oo YH, Doe GH. A qualitative case study on predicaments of spouses of people who inject drugs (PWID). The Three Millennium Development Goal Fund. [internet]. 2018 July [cited 2019 Nov 16]. Available from: https://www.3mdg.org/sites/3mdg.org/files/publication_docs/a_qualitative_case_study_on_predicaments_of_spouses_of_pwid.pdf
4. Bouchon M, Quétier M. Perceptions about drug use and harm reduction in Kachin, Myanmar. *Medecins du monde*. [internet]. 2018 Jan 8 [cited 2019 Nov 16]. Available from: <https://www.medecinsdumonde.org/en/actualites/publications/2019/04/01/perception-about-drug-use-and-harm-reduction-kachin-myanmar>
5. Parker RM, Jacobson KL. Health Literacy. *Emory Schools of Medicine and Public Health*. [internet]. 2012 Feb [cited 2019 Nov 16]. Available from: http://www.nationalacademies.org/hmd/~media/Files/Activity%20Files/PublicHealth/HealthLiteracy/HealthLiteracyFactSheets_Feb6_2012_Parker_JacobsonFinal1.pdf
6. Weiss BD. Health literacy and patient safety: Help patients understand. Manual for clinicians. American Medical Association Foundation; 2007.
7. Shuja M, Sarrafzadegan N, Roohafza HR, Sadeghi M, Ghafari M, Mohammadian M, Hafshejani AM. Factors associated with cigarette smoking in central parts of Iran. *Asian Pacific journal of cancer prevention: APJCP*. 2017;18(3):647.
8. World Health Organization. Health promotion. Track 2: Health literacy and health behaviour. [internet]. 2009 [cited 2019 Nov 16]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/healthpromotion/conferences/7gchp/track2/en/>
9. Fleiss JL, Levin B, Paik MC. Statistical method for rates and proportions. John Wiley & Sons; 2013 Jun 12.
10. Hosmer Jr DW, Lemeshow S, Sturdivant RX. Applied logistic regression. John Wiley & Sons; 2013 Apr 1.
11. HLS-EU CONSORTIUM. Comparative Report on Health Literacy in Eight EU Member States. The European Health Literacy Project 2009–2012; Ludwig Boltzmann Institute for Health Promotion Research: Vienna, Austria. 2012. [cited 2019 Nov 16]. Available online: www.HEALTH-LITERACY.EU
12. Sørensen K, Pelikan JM, Röthlin F, Ganahl K, Slonska Z, Doyle G, Fullam J, Kondilis B, Agraftotis D, Uiters E, Falcon M. Health literacy in Europe: comparative results of the European health literacy survey (HLS-EU). *European journal of public health*. 2015 Dec 1;25(6):1053-8.
13. Jovanić M, Zdravković M, Stanisavljević D, JovićVraneš A. Exploring the importance of health literacy for the quality of life in patients with heart failure. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 2018 Aug 16;15(8):1761.
14. Oo WM, Soe PP, Lwin KT. Status and determinants of health literacy: a study among adult population in selected areas of Myanmar. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*. 2017 Feb 5;2(3):318-22.

15. Rajah R, Hassali MA, Murugiah MK. A systematic review of the prevalence of limited health literacy in Southeast Asian countries. *Public health*. 2019 Feb 1;167:8-15.
16. Garcia-Codina O, Juvinyà-Canal D, Amil-Bujan P, Bertran-Noguer C, González-Mestre MA, Masachs-Fatjo E, Santaegúènia SJ, Magrinyà-Rull P, Saltó-Cerezuela E. Determinants of health literacy in the general population: results of the Catalan health survey. *BMC public health*. 2019 Dec 1;19(1):1122.
17. Pedro A, Amaral O, Escoval A. Health literacy, from data to action: translation, validation and application of the European Health Literacy Survey in Portugal. *Revista Portuguesa de Saúde Pública*. 2016; 34(3):259-75.